

Educational Leadership in the Digital Age: Basis for the Development of a Technology Integration Training Model

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ABSTRACT

The current study pertains to the explorations on the role of technology integrations towards the different educational practices in terms of leadership to be headed by the school principals and other administrators, for in this scenario, our current trend in the world of education sector builds up an educational transformation through digital transformation and modernization that will welcome the learners and the teachers in the explorations of modernized strategies and techniques in teaching and learning processes. The researcher will employ the quantitative research design. Quantitative research is the naturalistic study of social meanings and processes, using interviews, observations, and the analysis of texts and images pertaining to the study of digital transformation in education to explore the role of technology

information in educational leadership. The participants of the study are the 54 teachers from San Antonio District, Division of Nueva Ecija during the School Year 2023-2024. Educational leadership is needed to provide effective and workable plans and programs as the means of creating transformative digitalized schools and the explored technology integration shall be imbued. There is a very high significant relationship among all the managerial skills dimensions required of the institution administrators using the same managerial dimensions. The managerial skills of the administrators must be enhanced to improve the quality of people in the institution. There is a remarkable and valuable association between the accountability of the school head and teachers on the utilization of digital transformations in education in terms of the functionality of the technology integration to leadership education. To all least assessed statements on this current study will be the talk of the program to be conducted by the researcher as a training matrix pertaining to the digital transformation and technology integration as an innovative culture for the educational leadership.

Keywords: *digital transformation, technology integration, educational leadership, training model*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has transformed the educational landscape, redefining how schools operate, how teachers deliver instruction, and how learners engage with knowledge. The emergence of digital tools, learning management systems, artificial intelligence, data analytics, and online collaborative platforms has created new opportunities for improving teaching, learning, and school management. Consequently, educational leaders are increasingly expected to possess the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to lead digital transformation initiatives and promote effective technology integration within their institutions.

Educational leadership in the digital age extends beyond traditional administrative functions. School leaders are now tasked with fostering innovation, supporting technology-enhanced teaching practices, managing digital

resources, and creating learning environments that respond to the demands of the twenty-first century. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2023), effective educational leadership plays a crucial role in ensuring that digital technologies contribute positively to educational quality, equity, and accessibility. As schools continue to embrace digital transformation, leaders must be adequately prepared to navigate technological changes while addressing the diverse needs of teachers and learners.

Recent studies have highlighted the growing importance of digital leadership competencies among school administrators. Research by Dexter and Richardson (2023) emphasized that school leaders significantly influence teachers' technology adoption through strategic planning, resource allocation, and professional support. Similarly, the study of Sheninger (2023) noted that successful digital transformation in schools depends largely on leaders' ability to create a vision for technology integration and foster a culture of continuous learning and innovation. These findings suggest that educational leaders serve as catalysts for technology integration and organizational change.

Despite the recognized importance of digital leadership, several studies have revealed persistent challenges in the implementation of educational technologies. A systematic review conducted by Petko, Prasse, and Cantieni (2023) found that many school leaders possess positive attitudes toward technology but often lack the specialized competencies required to effectively lead digital transformation initiatives. Likewise, the findings of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023) indicated that while schools continue to invest in digital infrastructure, leadership capacity remains a critical factor affecting the successful integration of technology in educational settings.

In the Philippine context, the Department of Education has continuously promoted digital transformation through various programs and policies aimed at improving educational delivery and administrative efficiency. However, disparities in technology utilization, digital literacy, and leadership readiness remain evident across schools. Recent local studies have shown that many educational leaders continue to encounter challenges related to technological competence, strategic planning for digital initiatives, and the provision of technology-related professional development for teachers. These concerns became more apparent during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated the need for digital leadership and technology-driven educational management.

While existing literature has extensively examined technology integration among teachers and the impact of digital tools on student learning, there remains a limited body of research focusing specifically on the digital leadership competencies of educational leaders and how these competencies can serve as a foundation for a structured training model. Most previous studies have concentrated on identifying challenges and opportunities associated with technology adoption, but fewer have explored the specific training needs of school leaders responsible for driving digital transformation. This gap in the literature highlights the need for empirical evidence that can inform the design of leadership development programs tailored to the demands of digital-age education.

Furthermore, current professional development initiatives often emphasize instructional technology for teachers while providing limited attention to leadership-focused technology integration competencies. As educational institutions continue to evolve in response to technological advancements, there is a pressing need to develop a comprehensive training model that equips educational leaders with the necessary knowledge, skills, and strategic capabilities to effectively lead digital transformation efforts.

Given these circumstances, this study seeks to examine the extent of digital transformation and technology integration practices among educational leaders. Specifically, it aims to identify existing strengths, challenges, and competency needs that may serve as a basis for the development of a technology integration training model. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on digital leadership and provide practical guidance for policymakers, educational institutions, and professional development providers in designing programs that strengthen leadership capacity in the digital age.

Ultimately, understanding how educational leaders navigate digital transformation is essential for ensuring that schools remain responsive, innovative, and capable of meeting the evolving needs of learners and society. By addressing the identified research gap and proposing a contextually relevant training model, this study endeavors to support the advancement of effective educational leadership in an increasingly technology-driven world.

Therefore, this study seeks to assess educational leadership practices in the context of digital transformation and technology integration and use the findings as a basis for the development of a Technology Integration Training

Model. The proposed training model aims to address identified competency gaps, enhance digital leadership capabilities, and support educational leaders in fostering innovative, technology-enabled learning environments. Ultimately, the study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on digital leadership and provides practical recommendations for strengthening leadership effectiveness in an increasingly digital educational landscape.

Literature Review

Profile of the Teachers

The status of the teachers depends on the among those platforms, had the most promising effect on digitalized learning. Pritasari et al. (2021, cited in Firdaus & Mayasari, 2022), mentioned that the schools needed to imbue on themselves higher parameters in their status, most especially in their training backgrounds and even their years of experiences, such as on establishing their Learning Management System, that can deliver numerous features that educators led by their school heads for continuous utilizations on the digital transformations for learning tasks. Ferdianto and Dwiniasih (2019) also stipulated that students can do on and upload tasks, receive feedback, and work together with peers through the technology integrations and the digital outcomes on the transformations the schools about to be meted in the commodities of the school being led by them, which has been introduced to strengthen, empower and improve quality of learning so that all learners able to receive basic schooling and have the ability to inspire themselves to love of learning.

The utilization of e-learning technology can facilitate and support learning for those students who are ill and not stop them to gain their education without thinking left behind by other students and feeling obliged to attend every class and minimize the spreading of germs for the good of learning (Aggarwal, A., et al., 2015). Learning also can take place without putting a student's comfort and safety into difficulty. E-learning, as means of technology – based integrations, helps the school premises to have an alternative plan to deliver instruction despite unexpected bad weather happens. In my experience teaching here in the USA, we encountered a lot of bad weather that triggered the schools to transfer learning to online wherein the students need to work at home (Apriliansi, Asib, & Ngadiso, 2019). And because of these unexpected circumstances, the e-learning platform comes into a good idea to cater to the students' needs, provide support, access instruction and not be left behind (Acosta, et.al., 2017).

Extent on the Utilization of Digital Transformation in Education

Online learning, as part of the digitalized transformational system, has become a flexible and mode of modern teaching approach due to the rising of technology different platforms and internet infrastructure enhancement (Pei & Wu, 2019; Wang et al., 2021, cited in Bawa, 2022). Digitalized Learning has led to innovative solution and alternative support for schools and universities to overcome challenges regarding the continuous shortage of faculty members, the increasing number of students, lack of teaching resources (Wang et al., 2021, cited in Bawa, 2022) and time or space issues (O' Shea et al., 2015, cited in Alvarado, Sy, & Adriatico, 2019).

Awareness

Research into leadership awareness has evolved from a theory of universal traits and behaviors possessed naturally by all great leaders around the world, to a host of „contingency“ theories, whereby traits and behaviors of good leaders are contingent on situations, professions, and cultures (Zepp, 2018). Further study by Zepp, (2018), it revealed the differences between cultural perceptions of good and bad leaders. Philippine teachers valued honesty above all other traits and ranked intelligence only a lowly 5th, while other teachers in other countries valued intelligence as the most important trait of a leader (Arar & Abu Nasra, 2018). Even among Philippine teachers, there were significant differences between subgroups, namely between men and women, and between old and young teachers. These findings support other international research in the finding that not only do different cultures have different perceptions of leadership, but also that various subcultures such as men-women, old-young, and different professions, may view leadership in different lights (Vijayabaskar, & Sharveswara, 2019).

Vision for Transformation

E-learning is learner-centered which is like a shift from the traditional Learning which is teacher-centered, another analogous event where the school heads could enhance the vision for the transformative phenomenon for the digital set up and technologically – based school premise. E-learning improves access to information resources and enriches learning content. When the full potential of e-learning is realized, it will advance knowledge by expanding and broadening access, improving educational quality, and lowering costs (Newhouse, 2002, cited in Subedi, 2016).

Vision for school – based transformation offers several advantages, including ease of use, student safety, efficient tools, and resources for teachers in optimizing instruction, making lessons enjoyable, increasing learners' enthusiasm, self-confidence, and responsibility, encouraging students' critical thinking, overcoming issues of the large class, increasing students' motivation and autonomy, and developing students' positive attitudes toward learning outside of class (Rojabi, 2019). Furthermore, it is more efficient than traditional assignments that must be written on paper. Aside from being a paperless activity, it also aids teachers in data collection, storage, and grading (Ferdianto & Dwiniasih, 2019).

Moreover, there should be a well-balanced eLearning budget. There should be eLearning funds set aside for eLearning expenses such as purchasing eLearning foundations and building secure eLearning study halls, not to mention sending instructors to eLearning courses (Bartz, D., Thompson, K., & Rice, P. (2017). Schools can raise funds through fundraising, using funds provided by the Department of Education, or soliciting donations from organizations or even neighborhood organizations (Kupa, 2021, cited in Firdaus & Mayasari, 2022).

Responsibility

According to Cansoy, et.al., (2017), it was seen that the most important leadership qualities that should be brought to students according to the teachers' opinions are communication skills, problem-solving skills, responsibility, honesty, and goal setting, respectively as the means of creating greater responsibilities for the school heads to implore and explore the role of digital transformations and the technology integrations.

Ethics is the right conduct exercise by government officials from department heads to rank and-file employees (Oyelana, Kang'ethe, 2016, cited in Nguyen & Nguyen, 2022). There are five ethical climates, citing the works of Martin and Cullen: caring or concern for others; independent or a person own personal moral beliefs; law and code or the organizations' decision-making observing external codes; rules or prevailing rules and conduct; and the instrumental or the organizations' decision based on its personal interest (Wesarat, Phathara-on, Sharif, Halim, Abdul, Majid, & Abdul, 2017; cited in Rama, & Wahyudi, 2019). The involvement of ethics in public administration leads to a sustainable public administration which harvests productive and effective results. Ethical reasoning is the answer to the complexities of a situation and may provide a feasible solution. Hence, it means that ethics is the need of the public in case of difficult scenario (Almutairi, Hezam, Mahmood, Arahad, 2014; cited in Rama, & Wahyudi, 2019).

Accountability for Performance and Results

The accountability problem being faced by today's organizations in school – based is that they are either over led or under led thus they need to increase their leading capacities to exercise balanced leadership (Boudreaux, 2017). Generally, leadership occurs when there is a relationship between the leader (one who intends to lead) and the people who prefer to follow (followers). This study aims to review literature related to the qualities of a good leader and the benefits of good leadership to the organization with the aim to establish gaps for further studies on the topic (Muteswa, 2016).

Leadership is the most important facet/aspect of managing any type of business organizations be it a corporate with higher accountability levels, a single proprietorship, or a business partnership, whether it is a family business or be it simply a cooperative structure. No matter how big or small a company is, it must be managed effectively and efficiently for the staff to be even become more productive and satisfied to do their tasks (Aquino, 2015).

It is at this stage where culture of ethics is very evident and giving importance to needs of the people and prioritizing service to the public are the goal of the organization (Sable, 2015). Agency heads must be the role model of good governance and be an example of an ethical public servant and such transformation of local officials into an ethical leader-manager requires determination and conviction not only of the person himself but also of the institution (Aquino, 2015 & Brito, L. et.al., 2016).

Resources for Community – Based Learning

By using e-learning platforms, students enter a friendly environment which they may create themselves under the guidance of a tutor, they are very reasonable resources for a community – based learning while the utilization on the digital transformation exists (Alvarado, Sy, & Adriatico, 2019). Such collaborative platforms reunite a wide range of working teams (trainers and trainees), the information being widespread to the outer circles of the university. E-learning platforms, per se, meet the demand for sustainability tools in education, providing numerous advantages and opening the gates to new opportunities in learning. Learning oriented education has a better choice in using e-learning platform, students being able to build their environment through networking and connecting. They are also inclusive, allowing students from rural and/or remote areas to be part of the learning community. According to Salicru (2018), like other types of platforms, e-learning may be vulnerable and volatile in a competitive market and counterfeits are difficult to control.

Visioning resources creates a map of the future by painting a picture of new possibilities. It provides your people with the motivation to give up their current views and work out ways to change. Truly, the studies and literatures from abovementioned will be reconciled on this paper to be able to identify the justified reliability of the leadership capabilities and managerial performance (Zarra, 2019, cited in Firdaus & Mayasari, 2022).

Technology Integration in Educational Leadership

Thus, the technology integration market will be transformed by the entrance of millions of primary and secondary students and teachers going online. The internet enables students and teachers to expand their horizons and permits them to look elsewhere for better instruction, or more opportunities to teach, and this will be used by the school heads to integrate the technology – based commodities and the digitalized transformations for the school system and culture to be imbued (Saregar, Zubaedi, Parmin, Jamaludin, Anwar, & Septiani, 2019). Students and parents will increasingly access alternative or improved content and teaching from outside their specific school. No longer do students have to be limited by that teacher they don't get along with. And given that e-learning supports cheap, bite-sized, and sometimes free learning — this could mean that many students get a better quality of education. Or at least one more suited to their learning style (Majumdar & Calhoun, 2020; cited in Hearn, 2021).

Synchronous and asynchronous working gives teachers flexibility in preparing learning materials and enables students to juggle the demands of home and study. Teachers do not need to deliver material at a fixed time: it can be posted online for on-demand access and students can engage with it using wikis, blogs, and e-mail to suit their schedules, thus with the adherence of the school heads will become more comprehensive in the terms of the transformations and the technological transpirations (Vijayabaskar, & Sharveswara, 2019). Teachers can check on students' participation periodically and make online appointments for students with needs or questions. Having a pool of asynchronous learning materials gives teachers and students more room to breathe. Asynchronous learning works best if prepared in digital formats, even if some students use printed versions of the material (Kanwar & Daniel, 2020, cited in Kupa, 2021).

It was said by Cakiroglu et.al. (2017), that students' perspectives reflected that the main function of the digital transformation requires facilitated conceptual understanding via concretization, pausing, slowing down, replaying, and enlarging features. Along with the study findings, some implications were included for the use of videos and 3D animations in conceptual learning studies. Since the change in IT and the ways of interacting with computers are rapidly changing, students' understandings and conceptions about computers become challenging task to investigate (Rucker & Pinkwart, 2015).

Further research by Rucker & Pinkwart (2015) highlighted five basic conceptions about computers: computers are intelligent, omniscient databases, wire networks, mechanical, and programmable. Within the studies

about conceptual understandings, a wide variety of techniques are used in terms of determining and remedying the misconceptions, asserted that videos have unique features to enhance or support classroom-based and teacher-led learning approaches. Also, animations are considered as a means for supporting to organize the knowledge in the memory and facilitate to reorganize the schemas. Similarly, it points out that using animations can support learning using new software and hardware techniques. Some positive effects were noticed through 2D animations, and the advent of new techniques teachers began to experience the 3D. Because learning from 3D animations can facilitate learning with 3D objects and allow students to investigate events, objects, or concepts more accurately. Researchers concluded that incorporating animations or videos in instruction is useful especially when learning process requires visualization or motion.

Function

According to Valerio (2018), in addition, school heads must open their doors to continuous learning for organizational and personal development, innovation and change because improvement of oneself and the organization are important factors towards the attainment of good governance. Further, it is of paramount importance for the government officials to have political will in policy making and in the implementation of a good law, this is somehow an integral part of their occurrences because of the digital transformation and technology integration by means of explorations.

Institutions of higher learning face a new situation on higher education. It holds some novel threats and presents some fresh opportunities. Given the uncertainty of the future, college and university administrators cannot allow their organizations to drift (Magbojos, 2012, cited in Hernita, Arafat, & Missriani, 2020). Furthermore, all the managerial dimensions exhibited by the administrators, namely communication skills, self – leadership, managing the task effectively, managing the people effectively, managing interpersonal dimension effectively, and solving problems effectively, were rated often. There is no significant difference in the assessment of the three groups of respondents in terms of communication skills and solving problems effectively. However, there is a significant difference in terms of self – leadership, managing the task effectively, managing the people effectively, and managing interpersonal relations effectively.

There is a very high significant relationship among all the managerial skills dimensions required of the institution administrators using the same managerial dimensions. The managerial skills of the administrators must be enhanced to improve the quality of people in the institution. The Proposed Executive Development Program and Training Model are strongly recommended. The research unfolded that leaders have their own experiences and challenges in performing their functions in planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. Factors such as gender, age and the number of years managing do not exempt a leader to experience challenges. Remarkably, the educational attainment and years of residency abroad of a leader do not free them from being challenged on their management functions.

As the educational attainment of the participants was not a vital requirement to complete the study, the gathering of their degree finished helped the research to conclude that, not all school managers graduated an educational management degree to be selected or appointed in the position (Ancho, et.al. 2020). As per the analysis of phenomenological data made by Acosta, et.al. (2017), using an emergent strategy revealed that leadership attribute can be a leadership contribute that strengthens the magnanimity of leaders to exercise authority over their people within the bounds of prudent management. It can be concluded that as leadership evolves, new set of skills rises.

Technology Proficiency

Perhaps the potential power of an organization is to possess excellent or above average employees just to tell that the school heads might be above or at least satisfactorily performing as vision casters in giving priority on the digital transformation and technology integration explorations, through the elimination of average employees with continual education and the development of their personality. Although there are a lot of theoretical knowledge and concepts, the introduction of a competency approach is not quite a simple process. At first it means a change,

with the aim of improving performance across the organization. And these facts require a change for each employee (Misa, et.al, 2018).

Leadership training has been seen as one of the personal attributes just for the proficiency in harmony with technology be imbued by the school masters. Leadership training can maximize productivity, shape a positive culture, and promote harmony. Training provided should be able to help people gain crucial skills and allows the organizations to attack relevant, crucial, real-time issues. Leadership training program should be designed to increase effectiveness of leaders' professions by cultivating their leadership capabilities. Leader with experience exudes more credibility during their leadership tenure. Credibility therefore is an important component of leader's personal attributes. Credible leaders can influence followers; leaders are seen as a credibility model to employees (Libunao, et.al, 2017).

Abdullahi and Tijani (2019, cited in Kupa, 2021) posits that technology proficiency in computer – based schematic strategy shall be supported by means of collaborative learning process that provide many opportunities for developing communication skills and positive attitude towards learning. Seemingly, e-learning serves as knowledge management for effective dissemination and collection of information which can positively accommodate the ever-growing need of students in higher institutions of learning in Nigeria. Though, E-learning seems to be a innovative approach to service delivery, interestingly its concept is progressively becoming eminent in Nigeria higher institutions. This is because it seems to be more flexible and more cost effective to both teachers and students due to the possibility of accessing unlimited information in all areas of learning and which necessitate the introduction of distance education that could accommodate as many learners as possible at a time.

Development of Schools' Values

Educational leadership is needed to provide an effective and workable plans and programs as the means of creating transformative digitalized school and the explored technology integration shall be imbued (Johnson, 2019). The leader must be characterized with confidence, empowerment, vision span and good behavior, modest life, shared vision and will serve as an agent in reforming an institution. The re-engineering of the public sector relies on the transformational leaders and the active participation of the people (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2011, cited in Linda, Anggraini, Abdullah, 2020). The role of the local government units' changes as the demand of the position changes and thus, the local government personnel must possess the skills and knowledge to provide better services to the public (Legaspi, 2012, cited in Cruz, Villena, Navarro, & Garvida, 2016).

Remarkable/Significant Association Between the Profile of the Teachers and the Utilization of Digital Transformation in Education

School heads have different management and leadership styles in accordance to their status, different managing and leadership strategies preferences, and different reactions to different teaching methods. The utilizations on the digital transformation in education for a certain school provides students with a new learning environment. They now have more options for achieving good teaching and learning results with the addition of the new learning environment. They can select the tool that will assist them in improving their studies. They can improve the teaching-learning process by combining online and face-to-face learning (Astuti, 2019, cited in Nguyen & Nguyen, 2022).

Remarkable/Significant Association Between the Profile of the Teachers and the Technology Integration

There are no significant associations in the assessment profile of the three groups of school head respondents in terms of communication skills and solving problems in terms of technology integration, for some reasons, the effective management comes to worsts (Ochada & Gempes, 2018). However, there is a significant association in terms of self – leadership, managing the task effectively, managing the people effectively, and managing interpersonal relations effectively. There is a very high significant relationship among all the managerial skills dimensions required of the institution administrators using the same managerial dimensions. The managerial skills of the administrators must be enhanced to improve the quality of people in the institution (Ogawa, 2016).

Remarkable/Significant Association Between the Utilization of Digital Transformation in Education and the Technology Integration

According to Durodolu, O. (2016), there is a high association with remarkable idea on how to implement and execute the electronic learning as a becoming more popular to be the digital transformative scheme and the technology integration pattern for the school heads to create an approaching perfect role on innovative school set up, and it is gaining traction in educational systems around the world. Electronic learning is becoming increasingly important, particularly in higher education and in distance learning situations.

Training Matrix (For the digital transformation in education technology integration in educational leadership)

The Proposed Executive Development Program and Training Model are strongly recommended (Cruz, Villena, Navarro, & Garvida, 2016). The research unfolded that leaders have their own experiences and challenges in performing their functions in planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. Factors such as gender, age and the number of years managing do not exempt a leader to experience challenges. Remarkably, the educational attainment and years of residency abroad of a leader do not free them from being challenged on their management functions. As the educational attainment of the participants was not a vital requirement to complete the study, the gathering of their degree finished helped the research to conclude that, not all school managers graduated an educational management degree to be selected or appointed in the position (Ancho, et.al. 2020).

As per the analysis of phenomenological data made by Acosta, et.al. (2017), using an emergent strategy revealed that leadership attribute can be a leadership contribute that strengthens the magnanimity of leaders to exercise authority over their people within the bounds of prudent management. It can be concluded that as leadership evolves, new set of skills rises. These are the strengths, abilities, and common leadership practices demonstrated and employed by Philippine Schools Overseas (PSO's) administrators as heads of their respective schools.

The leadership attributes revealed in this study have provided opportunities for leaders to be emulated by other leaders of which these become their contribution to uplifting the leadership practice at the workplace. Contributory leadership skills as typified by Philippine Schools Overseas administrators are anchored to and are best expressed in the spirit of true service which enables them to take others' ideas and feelings into account while holding in trust the group's ideals, beliefs, and hopes which keeps them aware of others' needs while in turn enabling them to become progressive leaders and profound individuals.

The theories involved in this research study are based on the following theories: the anchored instruction theory and the laissez-faire style:

This theory of anchored instruction was proposed by American Professor John Bransford in 1992 at Vanderbilt University. This Anchored Instruction Theory stated that technology-based learning that students use the technology as the carrier, represent the reality of living world as focus to discover problems, makes learning everywhere and anytime, able to create and generate relevant questions, and ultimately solve the real-life problems. This theory showed the real life of the world that technology became the core contents of teaching and learning using educational technology. Students discover and help them understand and find solution to a certain problem with the help of technology -based learning.

On the other hand, the laissez-faire style is to minimize the leader's involvement in decision-making, and hence allowing people to make their own decisions, although they may still be responsible for the outcome. Laissez-faire works best when people are capable and motivated in making their own decisions, and where there is no requirement for a central coordination. In Lewin et al's experiments, he discovered that the most effective style was Democratic. Excessive autocratic styles led to revolution, whilst under a Laissez-faire approach, people were not coherent in their work and did not put in the energy that they did when being actively led. These experiments were done with groups of children but were early in the modern era and were consequently highly influential. According to Kleiner, "to determine which style is appropriate, it is necessary to determine the 'task maturity' of the group members".

Furthermore, there were several concepts on e- Learning as a learning platform to create a school with digital transformation in accordance with the explored roles of the technology integration as had been mandated by the educational academe for the leadership and management. This theory Anchored Instruction was proposed by

American Professor John Bransford in 1992 at Vanderbilt University. This Anchored Instruction Theory stated that technology-based learning that students use the technology as the carrier, represent the reality of living world as focus to discover problems, makes learning everywhere and anytime, able to create and generate relevant questions, and ultimately solve the real-life problems.

This theory showed the real life of the world that technology became the core contents of teaching and learning using educational technology. Students discover and help them understand and find solution to a certain problem with the help of technology -based learning. The existence of the living world is referred to as the “anchor,” and is one of analytical instructional models under the constructive learning theory.

In this theory Anchored Instruction, “Jasper Woodbury Video Series” is one of the famous examples and this video consist of 12 video adventures - CDs. Using this educational - based learning, students were able to identify and solve mathematical problems through those 12 adventure stories. This theory emphasized that each adventure story is designed under the U.S. National Mathematics Framework Standards issued by the U. S. National Association of Teachers of Mathematics.

Through each video adventure-episode provides students with a variety techniques and skills in analyzing and solving mathematical problems opportunities. With the integration of educational leadership onto the digital transformative assessments of this learning, students having collaborate and sharing of ideas to obtain a mastery learning to other fields such as natural sciences, social sciences, literature, history and other necessary knowledge and skills.

However, it is noted that even there is a well-developed ethical structure where personal values play a vital role in determining ethical behavior. The results further showed that unethical behavior in politics can be overcome by ethical leadership and permanent education in the field of values and ethical behavior. Hence, the process of introducing ethical climate should start from a good leader (Stare, Janez; Klun, Maja, 2017, cited in Sable, 2015). As a result, having good governance is dependent on the managerial, leadership skills and the existence of ethical climate in the public sector, local or national. Thus, it is imperative that an assessment must be conducted among government officials, and employees, specifically, the chief executives and senior managers of the local government units. These public servants are bound to work seamlessly to achieve sustainable development.

METHODS

Research Design

The researcher will employ the quantitative research design. Quantitative research is the naturalistic study of social meanings and processes, using interviews, observations, and the analysis of texts and images pertaining to the study about the digital transformation in education to explore the role of the technology information in educational leadership. In the concept of quantitative research, with statistical methods enable broad generalizations about populations, this method will be used to allow a fair and unbiased group of respondents will be chosen randomly among the population.

This research will be also a descriptive quantitative correlational method of research. The descriptive quantitative correlational type utilizes the survey questionnaire which is the distinguishable aspect of the technique for obtaining and analyzing quantitative data. This method was used in which the researcher to find out in describe the relationships among variables without seeking to establish the connection. According to Quaranta (2017), this research process is described in detail by allowing the respondents to experience all the aspects.

According to Hearn (2021), descriptive research is designed to address specific questions while exploratory research is more flexible and given the wide variety of academic backgrounds museum professionals bring to the field, it is important to allow a way to collect this data in the survey.

On the other fold, quantitative research is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on the testing. On the other hand. Under the quantitative type of design to be used for this study, a correlational approach will be utilized. Bhandari (2021) defined correlational research as the design that analyzes the links between variables without influencing or

modifying them. In this research design, correlational study aims to determine the relationship of variables between each other and can also predict the positive and negative factors involved. Schober et al. (2018) described correlation as a measure of a relationship between variables. In correlated data, a change in one variable's magnitude is linked to a change in another variable's magnitude, either in the same (positive correlation) or opposite (negative correlation) direction. Correlation is most used to describe a linear relationship between two continuous variables, which is written as Pearson product-moment correlation. For jointly normally distributed data, the Pearson correlation coefficient and Chi – Square Test of Independence are the commonly utilized (data that follow a bivariate normal distribution). For continuous data that is not regularly distributed, ordinal data, or data with releasable values.

Research Locale

The participants of the study will be the larger parametric vicinity of San Antonio District which will be based on the mandate of purposive sampling, for in this case, the researcher who wishes to conduct this study about digital transformation in education will be appropriate on the explorations of the roles of technology integrated by the teachers for their learners while their school head is mandated to monitor them in this event of the terms of educational leadership. The school located in Nueva Ecija will be known to be currently utilizing the digital transformations and the technology integration, where the school is currently having the teachers as the respondents, and in unison that they are using the innovations of the digital transformations and technology integrations.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of the study are 100 teachers from the San Antonio District, Division of Nueva Ecija, during the school year 2024 – 2025. The respondents of the study were selected through a stratified random sampling process. The selection of the number of respondents who are the teachers in the aforesaid locale of the study, which will be accomplished through the confidence level and margin of error sampling formula so also to utilize the sample size of the strata or per stratum.

Research Instrument

The researcher will utilize a self – made questionnaire pertaining to the study about the digital transformation in education for exploration on the role of technology integration in educational leadership.

For the reliability of the instrument, a self – made questionnaire will be pilot tested on the respondents who are not included in the real conduct of the study. The Alpha Cronbach test for reliability will be used to check whether the items are reliable and at least acceptable (Adeniran, 2019). The use of the Cronbach Alpha for the test of reliability of the instrument used by the researchers will be applied in this scenario. The Cronbach Alpha Test of Reliability for Pilot Testing will help the researchers ensure the reliability of the research instrument to be used for the progress of this paper.

Data Gathering

The researcher will provide survey questionnaires to the public elementary school teachers of SDO San Antonio Annex and SDO Nueva Ecija. Once the researcher has made the self-made survey questionnaires, this will be done by pilot testing and proceed with the computation of Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability, before proceeding with the survey proper, conducting the study about digital transformation in education to explore the role of technology information in educational leadership. The researcher will gather the responses of the respondents at utmost confidentiality in response to the mandate of the Data Privacy Act. The respondents of the study will be properly oriented about the research process that this study requires. They will also be informed of their rights as participants of the study. Thus, if they wish not to continue participating even if the study has already started, they may do so. The names of the respondents will be intentionally coded throughout the study to establish confidentiality and to protect their identities if some of these teachers would allow it in writing. The researcher shall maintain the confidentiality of the students' identities who will become the clientele of the study.

Data Analysis

The statistical treatments of data will be the analysis techniques as the quantitative part for the progress of the study, as follows:

The Cronbach's Alpha Pilot Test will indicate if the reliability measure is at least acceptable.

Frequency Distribution for the status of the respondents, who are the public elementary school teachers of SDO San Antonio Annex, Division of Nueva Ecija. Weighted Mean with corresponding descriptive Indices for the extent of the utilization of the digital transformation in education and the technology integration in educational leadership. The 4 – point weighted mean scale will be utilized for the extent level and assessments on the utilization of the digital transformation in education and the technology integration, respectively as interval types of data.

The Pearson R will also be used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the two intervals or ratio-type data, namely, the extent of the utilization of the digital transformation in education and the technology integration in educational leadership.

Chi – Square Test of Independence will be used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the two nominal types of data: namely the profile of the teacher – respondents from the San Antonio District, Division of Nueva Ecija and the nominal treated variables under the extent on the utilization of the digital transformation in education and the technology integration in educational leadership.

In testing the hypothesis, a 0.05 level of alpha was set. The actual significance was shown with degrees of freedom and its critical value is set for comparison and for decision rules. If the statistical value is significant, the null hypothesis is rejected; otherwise, it will be accepted. The t-test takes a sample from each of the two sets and establishes the problem statement by assuming a null hypothesis that the two means are equal. Based on the applicable formulas, certain values are calculated and compared against the standard values, and the assumed null hypothesis is accepted or rejected accordingly.

Ethical Consideration

This study will be conducted with full respect for the rights, dignity, privacy, and welfare of all participants. Before the data collection begins, the researcher will seek permission from the appropriate authorities and secure the voluntary participation of the respondents.

Participants will be informed about the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and their right to withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. Informed consent will be obtained before they take part in the study. They will also be assured that their participation is voluntary and that they may choose not to answer any question that makes them uncomfortable.

To protect the privacy of the participants, all personal information and responses will be treated with strict confidentiality. No names or identifying details will be disclosed in the presentation, analysis, or reporting of the findings. The data gathered will be used only for academic and research purposes.

The researcher will also ensure honesty, fairness, and objectivity throughout the conduct of the study. The results will be presented truthfully, without manipulation or misrepresentation. Proper acknowledgment of all sources will be observed to avoid plagiarism and to uphold academic integrity.

Overall, this study will follow ethical research standards to ensure that the participants are respected, protected, and treated fairly throughout the research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the descriptive statistics through frequency distribution for the profile of the teachers/respondents, the majority of them came from the age bracket of 26 – 30 years of age, while there were no respondents aged 51 and above. There were more female teachers than male teachers; the majority of them were married and not separated or widowed, and some of them were still single. The majority of the respondents were item ranked with teacher 1, and a minority of them were teacher 3, while the majority of them still currently possess a Bachelor's degree or even a Master's degree, with only a few having completed their Master's and Doctoral degrees. The

majority of them served between 4 and 5 years, while a minority of them have been serving for 10 years or more. Lastly, all teachers were equally distributed to attend the trainings and seminars on both technical and management and leadership learning development programs.

Based on the descriptive statistics through weighted mean with descriptions and verbal interpretations on the awareness indicator under the extent of the utilization of the digital transformation in education, very remarkable that only one got a highly evident interpretation, which was the “*Aware of the program or project being implemented in their schools when it comes to the utilization of the digital transformations.*” The rest of the other sub-indicating statements pertaining to awareness were all moderately evident, with the lowest or the least assessed statement, which was the “*Aware of the appropriations of leadership skills to be intended and applied for the transformative equity to obtain a higher quality of education in accordance with the digital utilizations.*” Overall, the awareness of the utilization of digital transformation in education is moderately evident with certain implications.

This means, it implies that the school is currently enhancing and maintaining the project implementations that will yield procurement plans for the school in performing such transformation digitally, yet they need to diligently improve their awareness of the leadership camaraderie to intend the mastery of the applications on the equitable and sustainable frequency on the higher quality of the multi – facets of academic atmospheres in accordance to the mandate of digital usage.

Other teachers in other countries valued intelligence as the most important trait of a leader, which needed to be pertained on the values formation on the digital literacy (Arar & Abu Nasra, 2018). Even among Philippine teachers, there were significant differences between subgroups, namely between men and women, and between old and young teachers. These findings support other international research in the finding that not only do different cultures have different perceptions of leadership, but also that various subcultures, such as men-women, old-young, and different professions, may view leadership in different lights (Vijayabaskar & Sharveswara, 2019).

By the descriptions of the vision for transformation as part of the assessments on the extent of the utilization of digital transformation in education, the highest assessment was that *the vision of the school is well implemented, even if the digital transformation exists.* The rest of the sub-statements on this sub-indicator were all moderately evident, with the lowest assessed statements being the following: “*The vision of the school is easy to understand, even if the digital appropriations on the transformative education currently enhancing its level of utilization values.*” And “*The vision can still be in current or in appropriation – based state while the digital transformation for the academic preferences will be based on the utilization factors affecting the academe.*” Overall, the evident moderation was present in terms of the transformative endeavor for the educators to foresee some foreknowledge in the actual digitalization of certain academic atmosphere.

This typically implies that in this vision for transformation, the school was still intact to conform to the transformative atmosphere in terms of digitalization in educational institutions yet they need to consider improving themselves on the understanding of the appropriations on the transformative welfare for the teachers and learners to enhance their level of valuable era of digitalization, so also in casting the visions for the correctness of the academic references on the basis for the appropriate utilization of the academe’s perspective in digitalization for academic progress.

This involves that the vision for school-based transformation offers several advantages, including ease of use, student safety, efficient tools, and resources for teachers in optimizing instruction, making lessons enjoyable, increasing learners' enthusiasm, self-confidence, and responsibility, encouraging students' critical thinking, overcoming issues of the large class, increasing students' motivation and autonomy, and developing students' positive attitudes toward learning outside of class (Rojabi, 2019). Furthermore, it is more efficient than traditional assignments that must be written on paper. Aside from being a paperless activity, it also aids teachers in data collection, storage, and grading (Ferdianto & Dwiniasih, 2019).

Pertaining to the descriptive statistics on the responsibility sub-assessments for the sub-indicator variable for the extent of the utilization of digital transformation in education, all statements were unanimously considered moderately evident, with the highest assessed statement being “*The responsibilities of the school head are clear while the digital transformation is in process for the appropriations.*” While the least assessed statement was the “*The responsibility of the school head is to function well the appropriations of the procurements on a well-rounded*

digital transformation while being in the process of the transformational activities given in their school premises.” Overall, the assessment for the responsibility sub-indicator for the extent of the utilization of digital transformation in education was moderately evident. This indicates that the implication for this assessment dictates the value of the school head’s reiterations on the clear responsibilities as well as the accountabilities to appropriately process the digital transformation yet they need to improve on the functions for the premises needed to be addressed as a whole without any minor or major conflict, or even if cannot be refrained, little by little school head needed to make necessary adjustments on the appropriations of the digital transformation whenever there are lots of preemptive forces.

According to Cansoy et.al., (2017), it was seen that the most important leadership qualities that should be brought to students, according to the teachers' opinions, are communication skills, problem-solving skills, responsibility, honesty, and goal setting, respectively, as the means of creating greater responsibilities for the school heads to implore and explore the role of digital transformations and the technology integrations. The involvement of leadership ethics in public administration leads to a sustainable public administration that harvests productive and effective results. Ethical reasoning is the answer to the complexities of a situation and may provide a feasible solution. Hence, it means that ethics is the need of the public in case of a difficult scenario (Almutairi, Hezam, Mahmood, Arahad, 2014; cited in Rama & Wahyudi, 2019).

It is highlighted in the description for the verbal analysis on the accountability for performance and results sub-indicator for the extent of the utilization of the digital transformation in education, the highest assessed statement was that *“The actions taken by the officials are realistic to practice.”* While the least assessed statement was *“The actions to be taken as a form of accountability and responsibility of the school head shall be in appropriations of the well-established functions of the technology integrations as well as the propagation of the will of the excellences on digital transformation.”* Overall, the sub-indicator on this assessment for the utilization of the digital transformation for education pertaining to the accountability for performance and results was generally evident in a moderated way.

Since it has been established on the basis of implying this result, the school is only involved in realistic exercising of the power to be more accountable in their sustenance of academic atmosphere and camaraderie, yet they need to create a study – based formula on the apportionment of technology integrations as well as the spreading of the exemplary skills on the acts of the digital transformation be exist at all times. Implying with this result simplifies that the accountability problem being faced by today’s organizations in school-based settings is either being over-led or under led that they might require them to increase their leadership capacities to exercise balanced leadership (Boudreaux, 2017). Generally, leadership occurs when there is a relationship between the leader (one who intends to lead) and the people who prefer to follow (followers). This study aims to review literature related to the qualities of a good leader and the benefits of good leadership to the organization with the aim to establish gaps for further studies on the topic (Muteswa, 2016).

Based on the descriptive statistics pertaining to the resources for the community – based learning as part of the assessments on the utilization extents for the digital transformation in education, the highest assessed statement was that *the school head is involved in the learning environment of the learners.* While the least assessed statement was that *the resources of the modern way of learning are well implemented by the school head for the appropriations on the technology integrations and the digital transformations.* This overall description of the resources on community-based learning tended to be moderately evident and to be followed by some implications. The implications for these were all about the sustenance of the involvement of the school head in learning environments for the learners, yet the whole village approached educational institutions like this Caranglan, they needed to pursue at least one modern way of resourcefulness on the implementations of technology integrations that bestow quality education coming from the culture of innovations for the digital transformative endeavor for thorough enhancements of the technology integrations.

By using e-learning platforms, students enter a friendly environment in which they may create themselves under the guidance of a tutor; they are very reasonable resources for community-based learning, while the utilization of the digital transformation exists (Alvarado, Sy, & Adriatico, 2019). Such collaborative platforms reunite a wide range of working teams (trainers and trainees), the information being widespread to the outer circles

of the university. E-learning platforms, per se, meet the demand for sustainability tools in education, providing numerous advantages and opening the gates to new opportunities in learning. Learning-oriented education has a better choice in using an e-learning platform, students being able to build their environment through networking and connecting (Muteswa, 2016).

Based on the descriptive statistics pertaining to the teachers' assessments for the technology integration in educational leadership by which the assessment sub – indicator was the function, namely per se, the highest assessed statement to be most effective yet in a very moderate way was the “*The leadership and governance of the school head are well functioning while the technology integration is on the process for the digital transformations.*” The least assessed statement was that *the functions of the leadership and governance shall be under the actions taken listed by the school head that are in need to be well evident in effectiveness.*

Overall, the sub-indicator, namely the function under the teachers' assessments for the technology integration in educational leadership, was moderately effective. This implies that leadership and governance to be performed by the school head will be well-appropriated if appropriate digital transformation is imposed, yet the implementation of the effectiveness of the actions taken enlisted is a great challenge for them, which will be dealt with accordingly in research-based paper to establish an effective academic atmosphere for the rest of the function system for the digital integration.

Institutions of higher learning face a new situation in higher education. It holds some novel threats and presents some fresh opportunities. Given the uncertainty of the future, college and university administrators cannot allow their organizations to drift (Magbojos, 2012, cited in Hernita, Arafat, & Missriani, 2020). Furthermore, all the managerial dimensions exhibited by the administrators, namely communication skills, self – leadership, managing the task effectively, managing the people effectively, managing interpersonal dimension effectively, and solving problems effectively, were rated often.

There is no significant difference in the assessment of the three groups of respondents in terms of communication skills and solving problems effectively. The internet enables students and teachers to expand their horizons and permits them to look elsewhere for better instruction, or more opportunities to teach, and this will be used by the school heads to integrate the technology – based commodities and the digitalized transformations for the school system and culture to be imbued (Saregar, Zubaedi, Parmin, Jamaludin, Anwar, & Septiani, 2019). Students and parents will increasingly access alternative or improved content and teaching from outside their specific school. No longer do students have to be limited by a teacher they don't get along with. And given that e-learning supports cheap, bite-sized, and sometimes free learning, this could mean that many students get a better quality of education. Or at least one more suited to their learning style (Majumdar & Calhoun, 2020; cited in Hearn, 2021).

On the descriptive statistics for the technology proficiency under the assessments of the teachers' judgments pertaining to the technology integration in educational leadership, the highest assessed statement was The school head entertained the queries of the learners and parents pertaining to the proficiency-based technology integrations for the academic betterment in their atmosphere of learning camaraderie. While the least assessed was the technological resources for the learners are well solved by the school head as well as the school learning materials being well organized during the digital transformations so that the balancing of the necessities and demands for the integration of digitalized technology will be addressed accordingly.

Overall, the assessment of the teachers on the technology integration in educational leadership was moderately effective in terms of technology proficiency. This implies that the implementation of educational leadership with technology integration can be accomplished and accommodated through the atmosphere of at least proficient parents and learners, yet the school is in need of support to maintain this since the looming problem was on how to balance necessities and demands for the most wanted integration of digitalized technology, which will be addressed as a whole institution. Although there is a lot of theoretical knowledge and concepts, the introduction of a competency approach is not a simple process.

At first, it means a change, with the aim of improving performance across the organization. And these facts require a change for each employee (Misa, et al., 2018). Leadership training has been seen as one of the personal attributes, just for the proficiency in harmony with technology be imbued by the school masters. Leadership training

can maximize productivity, shape a positive culture, and promote harmony. Training provided should be able to help people gain crucial skills and allow the organizations to attack relevant, crucial, real-time issues. The leadership training program should be designed to increase the effectiveness of leaders' professions by cultivating their leadership capabilities.

A leader with experience exudes more credibility during their leadership tenure. Credibility, therefore, is an important component of a leader's personal attributes. Credible leaders can influence followers; leaders are seen as a credibility model to employees (Libunao et al., 2017). Perhaps the most incredible potential power of an organization is to possess excellent or above-average employees, just to tell that the school heads might be above or at least satisfactorily performing as vision casters in giving priority to the digital transformation and technology integration explorations, through the elimination of average employees with continual education and the development of their personality. Abdullahi and Tijani (2019, cited in Kupa, 2021) posit that technology proficiency in computer – based schematic strategy shall be supported by means of a collaborative learning process that provides many opportunities for developing communication skills and a positive attitude towards learning.

As it was mentioned a while ago during the resource for community – based learning, students and parents will increasingly access alternative or improved content and teaching from outside their specific school. No longer do students have to be limited by a teacher they don't get along with. And given that e-learning supports cheap, bite-sized, and sometimes free learning, this could mean that many students get a better quality of education. Or at least one more suited to their learning style (Majumdar & Calhoun, 2020; cited in Hearn, 2021).

Both statements pertinently The school develops the values and ethics inside the technology appropriations like being responsible, disciplined, careful, respectful, and critical thinker as mandated by the school head or principal, and the school head can be exposed to artists, performers, composers, and other analogous professionals that can enhance the technology integrations for the betterment of their school were all highly effective yet for the rest were all moderately effective. The highest assessment was the school develops the values and ethics inside the technology appropriations, like being responsible, disciplined, careful, respectful, and a critical thinker, as mandated by the school head or principal. The least assessed statements were as follows:

The school develops the unique facet of the field of specialty through technology appropriations on behalf of the school as a whole community as established appropriately by the school head or principal, and the school head improves the imaginative thinking and creativity of the learners and teachers in their school during the transformational strategies in technology integrations. Overall, the assessments of the teachers on the developmental atmosphere for the school values were all moderately effective.

This symbolizes the picture of the technology appropriations like being responsible, disciplined, careful, respectful, and critical thinker as established parametrically by the school head or principal yet they need to focus on the unique facet of field of specialty through technology appropriations on behalf of the school as a whole community with imaginative thinking and creativity of the learners and teachers in their school during the transformational strategies in technology integrations. Educational leadership is needed to provide an effective and workable plan and programs as the means of creating a transformative digitalized school, and the explored technology integration shall be imbued (Johnson, 2019). The leader must be characterized with confidence, empowerment, vision span, good behavior, modest life, shared vision, and will serve as an agent in reforming an institution. The re-engineering of the public sector relies on the transformational leaders and the active participation of the people (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2011, cited in Linda, Anggraini, Abdullah, 2020).

According to the measurement on the relationship between the Profile of the Teachers and the Utilization of the Digital Transformation in a remarkable way, through the use of the Chi -Square test of associations/homogeneity/independence established that unanimously were all significantly related the profile status of the teacher – respondents and the utilization of digital transformation since the computed chi – squares in each sub – variables for the profile status of the respondents were all greater than those of their respective critical values in accordance with the alpha error ruling and degrees of freedom policy. This implies that the status profile of the respondents tended to establish remarkable or exemplary occurrences on the basis of relating the stature of the teachers in utilizing their own pace and target to sustain proper appropriateness of digital transformation, which they needed to conform and to be transformed in the presence of educational leadership with educational technology

to suit them the special force of digitalized transformation. As a crucial component of leadership and management, remarkable leadership behavior stresses building an environment in which every employee develops and excels, which pertains to the utilization of digitalized techniques and strategies for the advancement of education. Leadership is defined as the potential to influence and drive the group's efforts towards the accomplishment of goals. This influence may originate from formal sources, such as those provided by the acquisition of a managerial position in an organization.

This somehow, to integrate the utilization of the digital capabilities as well as certain schools as a means of a transformative setup for learners and teachers, as we explore the necessities in their primary advancement of technological – based instructional abilities of integration (Arar & Abu, 2018). School heads have different management and leadership styles in accordance to their status, different management and leadership strategy preferences, and different reactions to different teaching methods. The utilization of the digital transformation in education for a certain school provides students with a new learning environment. They now have more options for achieving good teaching and learning results with the addition of the new learning environment. They can select the tool that will assist them in improving their studies. They can improve the teaching-learning process by combining online and face-to-face learning (Astuti, 2019, cited in Nguyen & Nguyen, 2022).

On the pursuit of a factual basis of remarkable measurement of associations between the profile of the teachers and the technological integration in educational leadership, since the computed chi-squares on each sub-variables for the profile of the respondents associated with the technological integration in educational leadership magnitudes were all or unanimously greater than those of their critical value, with the established ruling of alpha error and degrees of freedom, the researcher decided to reject the null hypothesis and to signify the closure property of verbal interpretations that the profile of the teachers and the technological integration in educational leadership was significantly related.

Thus, the implications will be that there is a remarkable association to strengthen the homogeneity occurrence on the stature of the teachers to integrate to themselves in teaching function the technological pursuits for appropriating the educational leadership purposes. This supports that in another context of study, there is a significant association in terms of self – leadership, managing the task effectively, managing the people effectively, and managing interpersonal relations effectively. There is a very high significant relationship among all the managerial skills dimensions required of the institution administrators using the same managerial dimensions. The managerial skills of the administrators must be enhanced to improve the quality of people in the institution (Ogawa, 2016). Though on the other hand, there was a point of view that there were no significant associations in the assessment profile of the three groups of school head respondents in terms of communication skills and solving problems in terms of technology integration, for some reasons, the effective management comes to worsts (Ochada & Gempes, 2018).

Based on the findings pertaining to the association measures with the utilization of the digital transformation in education and the technology integration in education, only the associations between the accountability – function variables tended to establish high correlation. While the rest of the sub-variables that had established their associations were as follows: under the average correlation were the awareness – technology proficiency and development of school values, responsibility – technology proficiency, and accountability - development of school values. For the moderate correlation, these were established on the following: vision for transformation – function, responsibility – function, and resources – community – based learning, function, technology proficiency, and development of school values.

Lastly, for the low correlation establishments, the awareness function, and vision for transformation to the associated variables, such as the technology proficiency, development of school values, and furthermore, the responsibility and accountability to the development of school values and the technology proficiency, respectively. This implies that there is a remarkable and valuable association between the accountability of the school head and teachers on the utilization of the digital transformations in education in terms of the functionality of the technology integration to the leadership education.

According to Durodolu, O. (2016), there is a high association with remarkable idea on how to implement and execute the electronic learning as a becoming more popular to be the digital transformative scheme and the

technology integration pattern for the school heads to create an approaching perfect role on innovative school set up as a form of the accountabilities for the school heads and the teachers for the students' welfare and to create remarkable functions on the site of academic atmosphere, and it is gaining traction in educational systems around the world. Electronic learning is becoming increasingly important, particularly in higher education and in distance learning situations. There is a very highly significant relationship among all the managerial skills dimensions required of the institution administrators using the same managerial dimensions.

The managerial skills of the administrators must be enhanced to improve the quality of people in the institution (Ogawa, 2016). Though on the other hand, there was a point of view that there were no significant associations in the assessment profile of the three groups of school head respondents in terms of communication skills and solving problems in terms of technology integration, for some reasons, the effective management comes to worsts (Ochada & Gempes, 2018).

CONCLUSION

It is much safer for the researcher to maintain the call for higher parameters of respondents; thus, when it comes to the profile of the respondents, this must be subject to terms and conditions to apply for the purposive criteria in choosing the status to perform such frequency distribution.

The school is currently enhancing and maintaining the project implementations that will yield procurement plans for the school in performing such transformation digitally, yet they need to act diligently in improving their awareness of the leadership camaraderie to intend the mastery of the applications on an equitable and sustainable frequency on the higher quality of the multi-facets of academic atmospheres in accordance with the mandate of digital usage. This typically implies that in this vision for transformation, the school was still intact to conform on the transformative atmosphere in terms of digitalization on educational institution yet they need to consider on improving themselves on the understanding for the appropriations on the transformative welfare for the teachers and learners to enhance their level of valuable era of digitalization, so also in casting the visions for the correctness of the academic references on the basis for the appropriate utilization of the academe's perspective in digitalization for academic progress.

This involves that the vision for school – based transformation offers several advantages, including ease of use, student safety, efficient tools, and resources for teachers in optimizing instruction, making lessons enjoyable, increasing learners' enthusiasm, self-confidence, and responsibility, encouraging students' critical thinking, overcoming issues of the large class, increasing students' motivation and autonomy, and developing students' positive attitudes toward learning outside of class.

This indicates that the implication for this assessment dictates the value of the school head's reiterations on the clear responsibilities as well as the accountabilities to appropriately process the digital transformation yet they need to improve on the functions for the premises needed to be address as a whole without any minor or major conflict, or even if cannot be refrained, little by little school head needed to make necessary adjustments on the appropriations of the digital transformation whenever there are lots of preemptive forces.

Since it has been established on the basis of implying this result, the school is only involved in realistic exercising of the power to be more accountable in their sustenance of academic atmosphere and camaraderie, yet they need to create a study – based formula on the apportionment of technology integrations as well as the spreading of the exemplary skills on the acts of the digital transformation be exist at all times. Implying with this result simplifies that the accountability problem being faced by today's organizations in school – based is either being over led or under led that they might need to increase their leading capacities to exercise balanced leadership.

The implications for these were all about the sustenance of the involvement of the school head in learning environments for the learners yet the whole village approached educational institution like this, Caranglan, they needed to pursue at least on the modern way of resourcefulness on the implementations of technology integrations that bestow quality education coming from the culture of innovations for the digital transformative endeavor for thorough enhancements of the technology integrations. By using e-learning platforms, students enter a friendly

environment which they may create themselves under the guidance of a tutor; they are very reasonable resources for community-based learning, while the utilization of the digital transformation exists.

Leadership and governance to be performed by the school head will be well – appropriated if appropriate digital transformation is imposed, yet the implementations on the effectiveness of the actions taken enlisted is a great challenge for them, which will be dealt accordingly in research – based paper to establish effective academic atmosphere for the rest on the function system for the digital integration.

Institutions of higher learning face a new situation in higher education. It holds some novel threats and presents some fresh opportunities. The implementation of educational leadership with technology integration can be accomplished and accommodated through the atmosphere of at least proficient parents and learners, yet the school is in need of support to maintain this, since the looming problem is how to balance necessities and demands for the most wanted integration of digitalized technology, which will be addressed as a whole institution.

Although there is a lot of theoretical knowledge and concepts, the introduction of a competency approach is not a simple process. At first, it means a change, with the aim of improving performance across the organization. And these facts require a change for each employee. This symbolizes the picture of the technology appropriations like being responsible, disciplined, careful, respectful, and critical thinker as established parametrically by the school head or principal yet they need to focus on the unique facet of field of specialty through technology appropriations on behalf of the school as a whole community with imaginative thinking and creativity of the learners and teachers in their school during the transformational strategies in technology integrations. Educational leadership is needed to provide an effective and workable plan and programs as the means of creating a transformative digitalized school, and the explored technology integration shall be imbued.

The status profile of the respondents tended to establish remarkable or exemplary occurrences since relating the stature of the teachers in utilizing their own pace and target to sustain proper appropriateness of digital transformation, which they needed to conform and to be transformed in the presence of educational leadership with educational technology to suit them the special force of digitalized transformation. As a crucial component of leadership and management, remarkable leadership behavior stresses building an environment in which every employee develops and excels, which pertains to the utilization of digitalized techniques and strategies for the advancement of education. Leadership is defined as the potential to influence and drive the group's efforts towards the accomplishment of goals. This influence may originate from formal sources, such as those provided by the acquisition of a managerial position in an organization.

The implications will be that there is a remarkable association to strengthen the homogeneity occurrence on the stature of the teachers to integrate themselves in teaching functions, the technological pursuits for appropriating the educational leadership purposes. This supports that in another context of study, there is a significant association in terms of self – leadership, managing the task effectively, managing the people effectively, and managing interpersonal relations effectively. There is a very highly significant relationship among all the managerial skills dimensions required of the institution administrators using the same managerial dimensions. The managerial skills of the administrators must be enhanced to improve the quality of people in the institution.

There is a remarkable and valuable association between the accountability of the school head and teachers on the utilization of the digital transformations in education in terms of the functionality of the technology integration to the leadership education.

References

- Acosta, A., et.al. (2017). From Leadership Attribution to Leadership Contribution: Leadership Skills and Abilities of Philippine Schools Overseas (PSO's) Administrators, *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, Volume 4(7)
- Adeniran, A. (2019). Application of Likert scale's type and Cronbach's alpha analysis in an airport perception study. *Sch J Appl Sci Res* Vol: 2, Issue: 4 (01-05)

- Aggarwal, A., et.al. (2015). Managerial Performance a Global Challenge: An Empirical Study of Psychological Factors as Performance Predictors, *The Indian Journal of Commerce*, Volume 68, Number 1
- Alvarado, E., Sy, F. & Adriatico, C. (2019) Constraints on School Based Management Compliance of Public Schools Principals. *Open Access Library Journal*, 6, 1-11.
- Ancho, I., et.al. (2020). Unfolding of Filipino School Leadership Experiences in Doha, Qatar, College of Graduate Studies and Teacher Education Research, Philippine Normal University
- Apriliani, A., Asib, A., Ngadiso (2019). Schoology as a learning media platform for writing skill: Implications to teachers and students. 3rd English Language and Literature International Conference. ISSN: 2579-7263
- Aquino, P. (2015). The Effectiveness of Leadership Styles of Managers and Supervisors to Employees' Job Satisfaction in Cooperative Organizations in the Philippines, *The Macrotheme Review*, 4(5)
- Arar, K. & Abu Nasra, M. (2018). Linking school-based management and school effectiveness: The influence of self-based management, motivation and effectiveness in the Arab education system in Israel. *Educational Management Administration and Leadership*. 48(1): 1-17.
- Bartz, D., Thompson, K., & Rice, P. (2017). Enhancing the Effectiveness of Millennial Teachers Through Principals Using Performance Management. *National Forum of Educational Administration and Supervision Journal*. 35 (4): 1-9
- Bawa, H.Y. (2022). Availability and utilization of electronic learning technologies for improving teaching and learning in tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Science and Technology Research & Development*. ISSN: 2955-0807
- Boudreaux, M. K. (2017). *Principals' Dispositions Regarding Their Autonomy in Site-Based School Management*. University of Memphis, Tennessee.
- Brito, L. et.al. (2016). Management Practices as Capabilities Leading to Superior Performance, *Brazilian Administration Review*, Rio De Janeiro, v.13, n.13.
- Brown, A. (2016). Brown: An Exploratory Study Investigating the Impact of a University Module that Aims to Challenge Students' Perspective on Aging and Older Adults. University of Cumbria. Volume 10, pages 25 – 39
- Cakiroglu et.al. (2017). The Use of Animated Video in Improving Students' Reading Skill (A Quasi-Experimental Study of Seventh Grade Student at a Junior High School in Jalancagak, Subang), *Journal of English and Education* 2015, 3(1), 59-79
- Cansoy, R. et.al. (2017). Leadership Development in Students: Teacher's Opinions Regarding Activities that can be Performed at Schools, *Universal Journal of Educational Research* 5(2)
- Cruz, Carol Dahlia P., Villena, D., Navarro, E., & Garvida, M. (2016). Towards Enhancing the Managerial Performance of School Heads. *International Review of Management & Business Research*. 5 (2): 705-714.
- Dexter, S., & Richardson, J. W. (2023). What does technology integration research tell us about the role of school leaders? *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 71(2), 645–662.
- Durodolu, O. (2016). Technology acceptance model as a predictor of using information system to acquire information literacy skills. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 1450. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1450>
- Ferdianto, F., Dwiniasih (2019). Learning management system (LMS) schoology: Why it's important and what it looks like. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1360/1/012034
- Fiorella, L., & Mayer, R. E. (2018). What works and what doesn't work with instructional video. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 89, 465–470. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.07.015>
- Firdaus, M., & Mayasari, S. (2022). Schoology-aided instruction: measuring the effectiveness for student-teachers' reading comprehension achievement. *JOLLT Journal of Languages and Language Teaching*, 10(3), pp. 380-391. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33394/jollt.v%vi%i.5311>
- Hearn, R. (2021). From Practice to Theory: An Exploratory Research Study of the Relevance of Museum Studies Curriculum to Museum Professional (A Dissertation)
- Hernita, R., Arafat, Y., & Missriani (2020). The Effect of Work Motivation, School Culture, and School-Based Management on Teacher's Performance. *Electronic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. 2(2): 188-202.
- Ibrahim, A. (2015). Thematic Analysis: A Critical Review of its Process and Evaluation, *West East Journal of Social Sciences*, Volume 1, Number 1
- Johnson, A. O. (2019). Science teachers' perception and readiness for e-learning instructional delivery in secondary schools in South West, Nigeria. *Review of Education Institute of Education Journal*, 23(1), 50–64.
- Kupa, R.C. (2021). Challenges and successes of implementing e-learning in ordinary primary schools in District 4, Tshwane South. Dissertation in University of South Africa
- learning interest on magnetism. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1155/1/012060

- Libunao, W., et.al. (2017). Exploring Leadership Capability Team Leaders for Construction Industry in Malaysia: Training and Experience, Colegio de San Juan de Letran Calamba City, Philippines
- Linda, R., Anggraini, C., Abdullah. (2020). The development of schoology as media to supporting blended learning on stoichiometry topic. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1655/1/012063
- Misa, J., et.al. (2018). Leadership Capabilities, Management Competence, and Performance of Elementary Public Administrators, *International Journal of Innovation and Research in Educational Science*, Volume 5 Issue 3
- Muteswa, R. (2016). Qualities of a Good Leader and the Benefits of Good Leadership to an Organization: A Conceptual Study *European Journal of Business and Management*, Volume 8, No. 24
- Nguyen, L.D., Nguyen, L.V. (2022). Schoology as an online learning platform to enhance english language ability for undergraduates in Vietnam. *Computer Assisted Language Learning Electronic Journal (CALL-EJ)*, 23(4), 139-161
- Ochada, N.R. & Gempes, G (2018). The Realities of Maintenance and other Operating Expenses (MOOE) Allocation in Basic Education System: Unheard Voices of Public School Teachers. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*. 7(4): 315-324.
- Ogawa, R. (2016). The Institutional Sources of Educational Reform: The Case of School-Based Management. *American Educational Research Journal*. 31(3): 519-548.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). *Digital Education Outlook 2023: Towards an Effective Digital Transformation for Education and Skills*. Paris, France: OECD Publishing.
- Pan, G., Sen, S., Starett, D., Bonk, C. J., Rodgers, M., Mikoo, M., et al. (2021). Instructor made videos as a student scaffolding tool: A case study. *Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 8(4), 298–311. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0360131513003072>.
- Petko, D., Prasse, D., & Cantieni, A. (2023). The role of school leadership in digital transformation: A systematic review of current research. *Computers and Education Open*, 5, 100142.
- Rama, A.N., Wahyudi, I. (2019). The use of schoology to enhance students' reading comprehension at Lakidende University. *Cetta: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*. ISSN: 2615-0891
- Rojabi, A.R. (2019). Blended learning via schoology as a learning management system in Reading class: Benefits and challenges. *Jurnal Linguistik Terapan*. ISSN: 20882025
- Rucker & Pinkwart (2015). Comparison of video instruction and conventional learning methods on students' understanding of tablet manufacturing. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 65(1), 53–56. Retrieve from: <http://archive.ajpe.org/legacy/pdfs/aj650109.pdf>
- Sable, C. (2015), Managerial Skills Development of Selected Private Institutions of Higher Learning in Batangas, Philippines, *International Journal of Business and Management*, Volume 3
- Salicru, S. (2018). Ten Leadership Capabilities for a VUCA World and Beyond, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323995232>
- Saregar, A., Zubaedi, Parmin, Jamaludin, W., Anwar, C., Septiani, R. (2019). Feasibility test Of mobile learning with schoology: Efforts to foster the students'
- Schmid RF, Bernard RM, Borokhovski E, Tamim RM, Abrami PC, Surkes MA, Wade CA, and Woods J. (2021). The effects of technology use in postsecondary education: A meta-analysis of classroom applications. *Computers & Education*, 72, 271-291. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0360131513003072>
- Schoonenboom, S & Johnson, A. (2017). *The Practice of Social Research*. 12th ed. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage, 2010; Muijs, Daniel. *Doing Quantitative Research in Education with SPSS*. 2nd edition. London: SAGE Publications, 2017.
- Sheninger, E. (2023). *Digital Leadership: Changing Paradigms for Changing Times* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Subedi, J. (2016). The Dimensions of Transformational Leadership in Urban School Leaders: A Mixed Methods Study, *California State Polytechnic University, Pomona, United States*. <http://localhost/files/x920fz764>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2023). *Global Education Monitoring Report 2023: Technology in Education—A Tool on Whose Terms?* Paris, France: UNESCO.
- Valerio, L. (2018). An Assessment of Managerial and Leadership Competencies and Ethical Climate of Local Government Chief Executives and Senior Managers in the Municipality of Santa Maria, Bulacan: Basis for Good Governance, *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Volume 191
- Vijayabaskar, V. & Sharveswara, R. (2019). Effectiveness of School-Based Management in Empowering the Leadership in Schools. Conference: International Conference Uva Wellassa University, at Baddulla
- Zepp, R. (2018), Perceptions of Good and Bad Leaders by the Philippine Teachers, *Journal of Management and Strategy*, Volume 9, Number 1

Zuowei Zhao & Lihua Fu (2018). The Effectiveness of Video Clips to Enhance Students' Achievement and Motivation on History Learning and Facilitation World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Educational and Pedagogical Sciences Vol:13, No:7, 2018